

Parental Awareness and Involvement in the Implementation of Institutional Activities

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Abstract:

Taking a closer look at allied variables alongside parental awareness and involvement can uncover new insights, enhance understanding of the implementation of institutional activities, and design approaches to promote meaningful parental engagement in the academe. In this context, this study aimed to determine the level of parental awareness and involvement in implementing institutional activities in selected sectarian schools for the School Year 2022-2023. Data needed for this study was collected from 190 parents of Grade 10 learners from seven academies of Central Philippines using a self-made data-gathering instrument that passed the rigorous validity and reliability tests. Findings revealed a high parental awareness and involvement in institutional activities. This study result calls for the enhancement of items registering the lowest mean under parental awareness and involvement, i.e., communication, parenting, decision-making, and Christian formation. However, parents have the same perception of awareness and involvement in the implementation of institutional activities.

Keywords: Parental Awareness, Parental Involvement, Implementation, Christian Formation, Decision-Making, Negros Occidental, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The phrase "It takes a village to train a child" (Prieto et al., 2019, p.67) underscores the notion that the responsibility for nurturing and educating a child extends beyond the immediate family to the wider community. Rasi (2020) stressed the writing of Ellen G. White that training the children and the youth to form Christian education is the first duty of parents, starting in the home and later working in cooperation with teachers and church leaders. Parents are recognized as essential partners in their children's educational journey, contributing significantly to their academic achievement and well-being. However, the extent of parental awareness and involvement in implementing institutional activities remains a critical area of inquiry.

Current State of Knowledge

George Armitage Miller's theory of information processing explains how our brains record, store, and retrieve information. This affects a person's motivation and behavior. As a result, individual actions and behaviors influence society as a whole (Bouchrika, 2022). The above-mentioned idea supports one of the features of Grolnick and Slowiaczek's theory, which emphasizes that parents should be informed about their children's education since knowledge acquired by parents encourages conduct (National Louis University and Cerezci, 2021).

Ahmetoğlu (2017) suggests that parents can stay informed about their children's schooling by participating in activities like parent-teacher conferences, volunteering in classrooms, and networking with other parents. Such will increase parental involvement in the child's educational process since it may be considered a form of parental communication.

Parental involvement in their child's education begins at home with a supportive, safe, healthy environment, appropriate learning opportunities, and a good attitude towards education (Đurišić & Bunijevac, 2017). Moreover, Epstein's (2019) study focused on the perspective of school and family partnerships. It presents five types of involvement that help families and schools fulfill their shared responsibilities: parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with the community. Added to this is the Christian formation of students' lives taken from the Adventist philosophy of education, which is based on the Bible and the writings of Ellen G. White. This seventh involvement type emphasizes cooperation among the home, the school, and the church in the Christian formation of students (General Conference of Seventh Day Adventist, 2003, policy FE05 and FE10, 2003)

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study on parental awareness is based on the information processing theory by George Armitage Miller, a key figure in the development of cognition studies and a pioneer of the information processing model in psychology (Bouchrika, 2022). This theory describes how individuals handle the information they acquire. In contrast, the study on parental involvement was grounded in Joyce Epstein's theory of overlapping influences of families and schools on children's learning and development. Epstein's research primarily emphasized the collaboration between schools and families, outlining five types of involvement that enable both entities to jointly support children's educational and developmental needs. Additionally, her theory explores a sixth type of involvement, incorporating the community as another influential factor.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine levels of parental awareness and involvement in implementing institutional activities of a selected sectarian school in the Central Philippines for the school year 2022- 2023. Specifically, this study sought to determine 1) the level of parental awareness in implementing institutional activities in selected sectarian schools in Central Philippines when analyzed in terms of communication, parenting, decision-making, and Christian formation; 2.) the level of parental involvement in the implementation of institutional activities in selected sectarian schools in Central Philippines when analyzed in terms of communication, parenting, decision-making, and Christian formation.

Research Methodology:

This section describes the study's methodology, including the research design, respondents, research instruments, data collection process, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The researcher utilized the descriptive research method to accurately describe the current phenomena. The fact that descriptive research identifies is already available. The researcher employed research tools like test questionnaires to get the available data. In the words of Atmowardoyo (2018), the primary objective of descriptive research is to systematically describe the events being studied.

Respondents

This paper used stratified purposive sampling to determine the respondents via the Cochran formula ($N=374$; $n=190$).

Data Collection Procedures

The data-gathering procedure involved obtaining permission from authorities, reproducing questionnaires, administering them to target respondents, retrieving the questionnaires, and then analyzing and interpreting the data.

Data Analysis/ Statistical Treatment

This study utilized analytical approaches consistent with the study's research objectives. Objectives 1 and 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine parental awareness and involvement in school activities in selected sectarian schools in Central Philippines when analyzed regarding communication, parenting, decision-making, and Christian formation.

Ethical Considerations

This study prioritizes the safety and privacy of its participants by ensuring confidentiality and anonymity throughout the research process. Consent was obtained beforehand, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw. No personal data that could identify participants was collected, adhering to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participants were assured that their identity would not be disclosed without consent, except when absolutely necessary. All collected materials were securely disposed of, with no chance of future retrieval.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the gathered data concerning its research objectives.

Level of Parental Awareness in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Selected Sectarian Schools in Central Philippines

Table 1
Level of Parental Awareness in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Communication

Items	Mean	Interpretation
My child's school ...		
1. provides their contact numbers and, asks for my phone number for easy communication access and promptly respond to inquiries.	4.20	High Level
2. provides an email address where parents can send and receive input or ideas on school policies.	3.87	High Level
3. sends me information on my child's activities at school.	3.86	High Level
4. assists me in understanding my child's physical, mental, social, and spiritual needs.	3.81	High Level
5. provides information to families on how to monitor and manage schoolwork at home.	3.77	High Level
6. discusses my child's progress in school before and right after the PTA meeting.	3.87	High Level
7. informs parents during PTA meetings about how the school works with local businesses and the local Adventist community to enhance students' learning and education.	4.24	High Level
8. gives information on community events I may want to attend with my child.	3.93	High Level
9. informs the parents that the school offers remedial and enrichment classes to students about to fail.	3.93	High Level
10. invites me to school events such as SG Days, Student Week of Prayer, and Periodical Awarding Ceremony.	3.82	High Level
Mean	3.93	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations indicate that parents generally perceived high awareness and communication from their child's school across various aspects. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Informs parents during PTA meetings on how the school works with local businesses and the local Adventist community to enhance student's learning and education," with a mean score of 4.24, indicating an exceptionally high level of communication in this area.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score is for the item "Provides information to families on how to monitor and manage schoolwork at home," with a still respectable mean score of 3.77, suggesting a slightly lower but still substantial level of awareness in this aspect. The high mean scores across all items imply a commendable effort by the school to maintain effective communication with parents. The result further suggests that parents were well aware of the implementation of school activities.

Constantino (2021) emphasized that communicating with parents is not just compliance but with the purpose of informing, as an effective communication with parents that builds relationships. The insight from Đurišić & Bunijevac (2017), highlighting the potential perception gap between teachers and parents regarding support and discipline, emphasized the importance of effective communication. The study's results, indicating a high level of awareness among parents, suggested that efforts in communication can contribute to bridging such perception gaps and fostering a collaborative relationship between teachers and parents.

Table 2
Level of Parental Awareness in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Parenting

Items	Mean	Interpretation
My child's school ...		
1. educates me as a parent on the importance of doing my part at home to promote my child's learning.	3.86	High Level
2. encourages me to report any concerns my child has at home to the school for assistance.	3.74	High Level
3. communicates with me the importance of assisting with my child's homework, which requires him/her to talk with me about things learned in class.	3.62	High Level
4. encourages me to explore additional knowledge from time to time as I review the schoolwork my child brings home.	3.63	High Level
5. asks me to emphasize to my child the importance of values taught in school and consistently promote and apply them at home.	3.84	High Level
6. informs me to visit my child at school and talk to my child's subject teachers and class adviser about any concerns that need to be	3.66	High Level

addressed.		
7. encourages me to talk with my child about their friends and other concerns at school.	3.48	Moderate Level
8. motivates me to join the family support programs with parent-to-parent discussion groups that the school conducts.	3.64	High Level
9. encourages me to attend the PTA meeting to learn how other parents motivate their children to learn.	4.21	High Level
10. emphasizes the benefits of allowing my child to participate in singing groups and clubs such as Pathfinders Club, Science Club, English Club, and other clubs that may improve my child's talents.	4.16	High Level
Mean	3.78	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations indicate a generally high level of parental awareness and engagement in various aspects related to their role in supporting their child's education. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Encourages me to attend the PTA meeting so that I can learn how other parents motivate their children to learn," with a mean score of 4.21, indicating a particularly strong emphasis on parental involvement in PTA meetings. On the other hand, the lowest mean score is for the item "Encourages me to talk with my child about his/her friends and other concerns at school," with a still respectable mean score of 3.48, suggesting a slightly lower but still moderate level of emphasis in this aspect.

The high mean scores across all items highlight the school's commendable efforts in fostering parental engagement and awareness in their child's education. The emphasis on attending PTA meetings, participating in family support programs, and encouraging children to join various clubs underscores the importance of a holistic approach to education involving parents and students.

This aligned with the study published by (Ahmetoğlu, 2017) and the recommendation from Lasater (2016) that parents could be informed about their child's school affairs through their interactions and exchange of information with school administration, teachers, and the classroom environment through several activities such as parent-teacher conferences, volunteering in their children's classrooms, and meeting other parents at their children's schools is essential.

Table 3
Level of Parental Awareness in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Decision-making

Items	Mean	Interpretation
My child's school ...		
1. Involves parents in numerous committees, such as curriculum, budget, handbook revision, and other improvement committees, to help determine the school's success.	3.51	High Level
2. announces to parents about the formal network developed to link all families with their parent representatives for decision-making.	3.56	High Level
3. assists parents in understanding the school's policy before and during enrolment.	4.06	High Level
4. encourages me to participate as a parent at the Parents and Teachers Association (PTA) Meeting to discuss and decide on important school-related activities.	4.23	High Level
5. motivates me to attend the PTA meeting because fundraising for school activities and programs that require parents' consent are discussed and approved.	4.08	High Level
6. emphasizes the significance of having parent representatives on every School Council, School Improvement Team, and other school-related committees so parents have a voice in decision-making.	3.87	High Level
7. allows parents to make important school-related decisions without the influence of school officials.	3.76	High Level
8. notifies the parents of any changes to the decision made after the PTA meeting to avoid confusion and conflict.	3.91	High Level
9. informs parents that their decision to volunteer to keep the school garden and campus clean is greatly appreciated.	3.71	High Level
10. tells parents that our decision to cooperate in school events such as camping, mission trips, family potlucks, and "Bayanihan" is critical.	4.11	High Level
Mean	3.88	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations indicate that parents perceived a high level of involvement and awareness in various aspects of decision-making within the school. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Encourages me to participate as a parent at the Parents and Teachers Association (PTA) Meeting in discussing and deciding on important school-related activities," with a mean score of 4.23, highlighting a strong emphasis on parental participation in decision-making processes.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score is for the item "Involves parents in numerous committees, such as curriculum, budget, handbook revision, and other improvement committees, to help decide on the school's success," with a still commendable mean score of 3.51, suggesting a slightly lower but still substantial level of involvement in this particular aspect.

The high mean scores across all items signify a robust commitment by the school to involve parents in decision-making processes, fostering a sense of collaboration and shared responsibility. Furthermore, the parents believed they were well-informed about several areas of school decision-making. Moreover, the result implies that there needed to be more clarity about implementation when everyone was aware of what had been decided.

The exceptionally high score for encouraging parents to participate in PTA meetings aligns with the broader literature emphasizing the importance of parent-teacher collaboration in decision-making for the school's overall success (Wati & Sahid, 2022). It suggests that the school recognizes and values parents' input in shaping key aspects of the educational experience.

Table 4
Level of Parental Awareness in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Christian Formation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
My child's school ...		
1. conducts an orientation on how this school handles the students' misbehavior and the procedures for implementing child discipline.	4.13	High Level
2. emphasizes to parents that the school's method of applying discipline is part of Christian formation.	4.30	High Level
3. informs parents about Adventist Christian Education's holistic approach to shaping children in the direction they should go.	4.40	High Level
4. works with families of students having academic or behavioral problems.	3.98	High Level
5. holds parent-teacher conferences with me to assist my child's spiritual growth. This meeting happens in addition to the Parents and Teachers Association or PTA meetings.	3.92	High Level
6. explains the significance of the parent-teacher partnership in developing a child's character.	4.06	High Level
7. acquaints me with how the school principal, subject teachers, and class advisers work together to foster my child's spiritual development.	4.01	High Level
8. emphasizes that religious education at home is as important as or even more important than that at school.	4.22	High Level
9. highlights the importance of allowing my child to participate in religious and other programs that help to shape my child's Christian character.	4.27	High Level
10. informs parents that religious programs at school and devotionals done in the classrooms and before big events begin to foster my child's spiritual growth.	4.22	High Level
Mean	4.15	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations reveal that parents perceived a high level of engagement and awareness in various aspects related to the Christian formation of their children within the school. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Informs parents about Adventist Christian Education's holistic approach to shaping children in the direction they should go," with a mean score of 4.40, indicating a particularly strong emphasis on the holistic nature of Christian education.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score was for the item "Holds parent-teacher conferences with me to assist my child's spiritual growth. This meeting happens in addition to Parents and Teachers Association or PTA meetings," with a still commendable mean score of 3.92 suggesting a slightly lower but still substantial level of involvement in this particular aspect. The result shows that the school needs to enhance and remember the importance of the caucus with parents after PTA meetings. Discussing a child's spiritual growth is more intentional if taken in private than in parent-teacher conferences.

The high mean scores across all items suggest that the school significantly emphasizes integrating Christian principles into various aspects of the educational experience. The result further revealed that parents perceive a high level of awareness in different aspects related to the Christian formation of their children at school. Parents are well aware of the children's school philosophy as a Christian school and the direction of the school towards forming Christian students.

The insights from Beckett (2023) emphasized the redemptive and educational approach to discipline within Adventist Christian schools. The study's findings, indicating a high level of awareness in communicating the school's method of discipline as part of Christian formation, aligned with the idea that discipline is viewed as an opportunity for learning and character development. This redemptive approach to discipline contributes to a nurturing and supportive Christian environment within the school.

Table 5
Level of Parental Involvement in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Communication

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. inquire about the school's contact information and provide my phone number for easy communication and to ask appropriate questions about my child at school.	4.20	High Level
2. use the school's email to communicate, particularly to express my thoughts and views on school policy.	3.58	High Level
3. go to school and follow up with the teachers on the reports I received from the school.	3.81	High Level
4. cooperate with the teachers as they assist me in understanding my child's physical, mental, social, and spiritual needs.	4.06	High Level
5. follow the given information to parents on monitoring and managing schoolwork at home.	4.05	High Level
6. discuss with my child's teachers my child's progress in school before and after PTA meetings.	3.86	High Level
7. assist in establishing links between the school and other institutions to improve my child's learning.	3.86	High Level
8. respond to school information regarding community events I might wish to attend with my child.	3.97	High Level
9. I regularly check my child's progress and request advice and remedial/enrichment classes whenever needed.	3.93	High Level
10. find ways to participate in school events such as SG Days, Student Week of Prayer, and Periodical Awarding Ceremony, despite my busy schedule.	3.89	High Level
Mean	3.92	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations suggest that parents exhibited a high level of engagement and participation in various communication-related activities with the school. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Inquire about the school's contact information and provide my phone number for easy communication and to ask appropriate questions about my child at school," with a mean score of 4.20, demonstrating a strong partnership between parents and teachers in realizing the value of two-way communication and meeting the child's various needs more quickly. On the other hand, the lowest mean score was for the item "Use the school's email to communicate, particularly to express my thoughts and views on school policy" with a still respectable mean score of 3.58, suggesting a slightly lower but still substantial level of involvement in this specific aspect.

The high mean scores across all items imply that two-way communication is practiced. Also, the result reveals a commendable level of parental involvement in communication-related activities with the school. The particularly high score for exchanging of contact information numbers reflects a deep concern and strong partnership between parents and teachers. This collaboration was essential for addressing promptly the diverse aspects of a child's development, including physical, mental, social, and spiritual dimensions.

While the mean score for using the school's email is slightly lower, it still falls within the "High Level" category. Schools may consider exploring ways to encourage and facilitate more active use of email communication, recognizing it as a valuable channel for parents to express their thoughts and views on school policy. Improving communication through email can further enhance transparency and feedback mechanisms between parents and the school. The result further suggests that the use of school's email is not that substantial for parents to communicate their thoughts about school policy and the mean score suggests that parents use other platform than email to communicate with the school personnel. To encourage parental participation in policy evaluation, additional channels of communication should be provided.

The insights from Ahmetoğlu (2017) emphasized the importance of parental communication and involvement in the educational process. It also includes parents' interactions and information exchange with school

administration, teachers, and classroom environment through a variety of activities such as parent-teacher meetings, volunteering in their children's classrooms, and meeting other parents at their children's schools.

The study's findings, indicating a high level of involvement in various communication activities, aligned with the broader literature on the significance of parent-teacher meetings, volunteering, and other interactions for fostering a supportive and collaborative educational environment.

Table 6
Level of Parental Involvement in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Parenting

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. do my part at home to promote my child's learning.	4.33	High Level
2. report any concerns my child is having at home to the school for assistance.	3.96	High Level
3. despite my busy schedule, I prioritize assisting with my child's homework, which requires my child to communicate with me about what he /she has learned in class.	4.12	High Level
4. find time to read, review, and manage the schoolwork my child brings home.	3.92	High Level
5. do my best to emphasize to my child the importance of values taught in school and consistently promote and apply them at home.	4.27	High Level
6. make a regular schedule to visit my child at school and talk to my child's subject teachers and class adviser about any concerns that need to be addressed.	3.69	High Level
7. find ways to talk with my child about their friends and other concerns at school.	4.02	High Level
8. actively participate in family support programs, especially parent-to-parent discussion groups.	3.77	High Level
9. make time to talk with other parents before and after PTA meetings so I can see how other parents encourage their children to learn.	3.62	High Level
10. encourage my child to join and be active in different clubs such as Pathfinder Club, Science Club, English Club, and singing groups.	4.13	High Level
Mean	3.98	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations indicate that parents exhibited a high level of engagement and participation in various parenting-related activities that contribute to their child's education. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Do my part at home to promote my child's learning," with a mean score of 4.33, indicating a strong commitment to actively contribute to their child's educational development. On the other hand, the lowest mean score was for the item "Make time to talk with other parents before and after PTA meetings so I can see how other parents encourage their children to learn." with a still commendable mean score of 3.62, suggesting a slightly lower but still substantial level of involvement in this specific aspect. The result also implies that PTA officers need to enhance parents' interaction among themselves and share their parenting techniques for the betterment of their child's education.

The high mean scores across all items imply that parents understood their role in their child's education. And they don't leave every responsibility on the teacher's shoulder. It further shows that parents were actively involved in various parenting-related activities that support their child's education. The particularly high score for doing their part at home to promote their child's learning underscores that parents saw the importance of their support in collaboration with the school personnel in fostering a positive educational environment even at home.

While the mean score for making time to talk with other parents before and after PTA meetings is slightly lower, it still falls within the "High Level" category. This lowest mean score implies that the bond among parents needs to be strengthened. Hesitation and awkwardness in sharing the burden with fellow parents show the reserved and shy culture of Filipino people. Schools may consider exploring ways to encourage all the parents to share their parenting techniques and strengthen the bond among them. Improving interactions among them can further enhance the understanding and support of the teachers and will eventually provide better service to the students.

Parental involvement in the education of students begins at home, with the parents providing a secure and healthy environment, suitable opportunities for learning, support, and a positive outlook on school for their child (Đurišić & Bunijevac, 2017).

Table 7
Level of Parental Involvement in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Decision-making

Items	Mean	Interpretation
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As a parent, I...		
1. Volunteer to sit on some of the committees, such as curriculum, budget, handbook revision, and other improvement committees, to help decide on the school's success.	3.12	Moderate Level
2. use networks developed by the school to link all families with our parent representatives for decision-making.	3.39	Moderate Level
3. ask for clarification to ensure that I fully understand the school's policy prior to and/or during enrolment.	3.94	High Level
4. actively participate as a parent at the Parents and Teachers Association (PTA) Meeting to discuss and decide on important school-related activities.	3.84	High Level
5. attend the PTA meeting to discuss and support fundraising for school events and programs that require parental approval.	3.8	High Level
6. nominate appropriate parent representatives to serve as our voice in decision-making on every School Council, School Improvement Team, and other school-related committees.	3.63	High Level
7. make my decision regarding school-related activities without the influence of any school officials.	3.74	High Level
8. will bring it to the attention of the right personnel if decisions made during PTA are changed.	3.73	High Level
9. find ways to extend my effort as a school volunteer in keeping the school garden and campus clean.	3.37	Moderate Level
10. recognize that my decision to cooperate in school events such as camping, mission trips, family potlucks, and "Bayanihan" is critical.	4.01	High Level
Mean	3.66	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations reveal that parents demonstrated a high level of engagement and participation in various decision-making activities related to the school. The highest mean score was observed for the item "Recognize that my decision to cooperate in school events such as camping, mission trips, family potlucks, and 'Bayanihan' is extremely important," with a mean score of 4.01, indicating a strong acknowledgment of the significance of parental cooperation in school events. On the other hand, the lowest mean score was for the item "Volunteer to sit in some of the committees, such as curriculum, budget, handbook revision, and other improvement committees, to help decide on the school's success," with a mean score of 3.12, suggesting a moderate level of involvement in this specific aspect.

The high mean scores across most items suggest that parents were actively engaged in decision-making activities related to school events and policies. The result implies that parents did not solely depend on the teacher's decision; the parents took part in deciding school-related activities. Moreover, the particularly high score for recognizing the importance of cooperating in school events underscored the positive attitude of parents toward participating in various school activities.

The lowest mean score for volunteering to sit in committees indicates a potential area for improvement in parental involvement because it implies less participation in various committees, and volunteerism is not well practiced. While still in the "Moderate Level" category, schools may consider implementing strategies to encourage and facilitate more active participation of parents in committees related to curriculum, budget, handbook revision, and other improvement initiatives. Increasing parental involvement in decision-making committees can lead to a more comprehensive and representative decision-making process.

The citation of Joyce Epstein by Mahuro & Hungi (2016) underscored the significance of involving parents in administration, governance, and decision-making roles within schools. The study's results support the idea that parents' roles extend beyond the home, actively participating in school governance and decision-making processes that directly impact their children's education.

Table 8
Level of Parental Involvement in the Implementation of Institutional Activities in Terms of Christian Formation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. thoroughly review how the school handles child discipline and give my honest feedback, if any, to make it more appropriate.	3.97	High Level
2. collaborate with the school's method of applying discipline as part of my child's Christian formation.	4.09	High Level
3. cooperate with Adventist Christian Education's holistic approach to shaping children in the direction they should go.	4.26	High Level
4. inquire beyond the information I receive whenever the school	4.07	High Level

personnel contacts me regarding my child's academic or behavioral problems.		
5. respond positively if a request for parent-teacher conferences with me is made to aid my child's spiritual growth. This meeting is in addition to PTA or Parents and Teachers' Association meetings.	4.15	High Level
6. recognize my specific role as a parent in the parent-teacher partnership in the development of my child's character.	4.17	High Level
7. communicate with the school principal, subject teachers, and class advisers to bridge the gap as they work together to nurture my child's spiritual development.	4.05	High Level
8. integrate values taught at school and conduct family worship at home because I believe that religious education at home is as important as, or even more important than, at school.	4.25	High Level
9. allow my child to participate in religious and other programs that help to shape my child's Christian character.	4.38	High Level
10. encourage my child to join religious programs at school and devotionals done in classrooms and before big events begin because these will foster his/her spiritual growth.	4.33	High Level
Mean	4.17	High Level

The mean scores and their corresponding interpretations suggest that parents exhibited a high level of engagement and participation in various activities that contributed to their child's Christian formation within the school. The highest mean score was observed for item "Allow my child to participate in religious and other programs that help to shape my child's Christian character" with a mean score of 4.38, indicating a strong endorsement of the importance of participating in activities that contributed to Christian character development. On the other hand, the lowest mean score was for item "Thoroughly review how the school handles child discipline and give my honest feedback, if any, for making it more appropriate" with a still commendable mean score of 3.97, suggesting a slightly lower but still substantial level of involvement in this specific aspect.

The high mean scores across all items suggest that parents were actively engaged in activities that contribute to their child's Christian formation within the school. This further implies that parents were not merely onlookers on how the school molded their children into Christianity, but they, too, got involved in the way they could. The exceptionally high score for allowing children to participate in religious programs and devotionals showed a strong acknowledgment of the role of these activities in fostering spiritual growth.

While the mean score for reviewing how the school handles child discipline is slightly lower, it still falls within the "High Level" category. Schools may consider strategies to encourage parents to provide feedback on discipline methods, ensuring a collaborative and constructive approach to maintaining an environment that aligns with Christian principles. The results also imply that parents believe that the school handles discipline issues fairly and hence entrust this area to school personnel.

The insights from Bunnell et al. (2018) emphasized the ultimate responsibility of parents in the Christian formation of their children. The study's findings, indicating a high level of parental involvement in Christian formation activities, align with the notion that parents play a significant role in guiding their children in matters of faith and character development.

Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from this study propose significant insights. Firstly, it suggests that a heightened level of parental awareness could signify effective two-way communication practices. When parents are well-informed about institutional activities, they are more inclined to engage actively and lend support to the institution's endeavors. Secondly, the findings indicate that strong parental involvement reflects a strong partnership between parents and the institution. Parents who actively participate in various institutional activities demonstrate a deep-seated interest in their child's education and overall welfare. These conclusions underscore the importance of fostering communication channels and encouraging parental engagement to enhance the educational experience and support students' development within educational institutions.

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